

THE IMPORTANCE OF PRAGMATICS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4964664>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th June 2021

Accepted: 10th June 2021

Online: 15th June 2021

KEY WORDS

pragmatic competence, target language, speech act, communicative breakdowns

ABSTRACT

Successful language acquisition and interaction may not be built only by following a set of grammar rules and rich vocabulary, but also pragmatic norms of a target language which partially or totally can differ from others as the native. Before the adoption of communicative approach, the learning languages was regarded as similar with grammatical accuracy and linguistics. However, this focus has changed giving the major significance to successful communication with the aim of producing and understanding intended meanings appropriately in different settings. In Language Teaching pragmatics regards the acquisition of language use in social contexts in second and foreign language classrooms.

Sometimes misunderstanding and communicative breakdowns may occur as a result of not having enough pragmatic competence in the target language.

Accordingly, the main purpose of this research is to get EFL learners acquainted with pragmatic competence on the speech act of complaining using some effective strategies that will assist them to overcome their difficulties in successful communication.

Learning a foreign language includes not only acquiring all theoretical rules or skills, but also learning communicative competence. It regards to learners' grammatical knowledge as well as social knowledge about how and when to use utterances appropriately. For this reason, this competence is considered to be crucially important aspect to master the language. A skillful teacher draws attention to learners' language skills, such as speaking, reading, writing, and listening ones, but also their communicative competence so as to make them proficient

users of their target language. Here, we have another factor that while teaching a language to students, we as a teacher draw our attention to students' errors and mistakes while they trying communicating or doing tasks in the target language. However, we should change this approach to let them feel free to use the language. Certainly, this leads to us to make progress in our field much more than our simple approaches.

One of the most necessary basis of forming communicative competence in learners' education is communicative

approach because this competence such a competence which underlies the communicative approach to language teaching. The main principle of this approach is the ability to interact in the target language.

Language teachers as well as scholars and researchers in the field of applied linguistics have been appealing the necessity to incorporate cultural knowledge into second and foreign language teaching. (e.g., Lafayette, 1988; Moorjani & Field, 1988). Often times the crucial focus of second and foreign language teaching has been directed towards dispensing the rules of grammar and increasing the knowledge of vocabulary in the target language so that one can produce correct utterances in order to communicate. That is to say, competency in linguistic knowledge does not guarantee successful use of the language. In order to accomplish fruitful communication learners, need to be acquainted "Cultural competency".

Smith (1987a) claimed that forms of address, appropriate topics of conversation, and expressions of speech-acts (e.g., complain, apologies, agreement, disagreement, requests etc.) are perhaps more important to effective cross-cultural communication than grammar lexis or phonology. As we all know that language

cannot remain static and has been and will be evolving its form affected by historical, social and cultural contexts.

Every teacher should bear in mind while acquainting cultural contexts to raise students' pragmatic competence the role of technology is crucially important. Computer games may establish a new learning culture and that this may better cover the students' habits and attention. When kept in mind the potential that computer games hold, teachers or specialists should use them in class in order to enhance the students' learning capacities and to provide them with a better learning environment. Moreover, the role play games are also common techniques that encourage learners to use a wider variety of forms which assists to enhance students' pragmatic competence. Role plays are useful methods of practicing targeted pragmalinguistic forms in the classroom. Teachers are supposed to apply more authentic opportunities to practice in the classroom to prepare them for real interactions. Tasks can provide context and consequence that allow learners to produce and demonstrate how they would use pragmatic strategies in the real world. They are also particularly valuable in our learning contexts where authentic language use situations are harder to come by.

References:

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